

MANAGEMENT TRAINING AND INCREASE IN THE QUALITY OF TEACHING STAFF IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATION IN THE CONTEXT OF CHANGES OCCURRING AFTER COVID 19

Author(s)*: Vasilica DAMASCHIN ¹, Mihaela Luminita LUPU²
Position: PhD Student¹, Prof.²
University: Gheorghe Asachi Technical University of Iasi, Romania
Faculty of Industrial Design and Business Management
Email: vasilica.damaschin@yahoo.com ¹,

Abstract

Purpose - Identifying the factors that influence the increase in the quality of the entire educational process and the adaptation of a set of measures to modernize the teaching-learning-evaluation system and increase the professional (didactic) competence.

Methodology/approach – Application of a questionnaire to identify the digital skills of teaching staff and directions for the need for improvement

Findings – The hypothesis closest to the empirical findings is that the results of the use of digital technology in education depend on a variety of conditions, among which the competence of the teaching staff is the most important

Limitations/implications of the research – subjectivity of teaching staff, lack of interest, lack of time needed for improvement

Practical implications – Proposals for effective educational practices, innovative courses for the effective integration of digital technologies in education

Originality/value – This paper provides an overview of how early childhood education teachers deal with HR quality and motivation for improvement

Key words: reform, pandemic, efficiency, performance

Introduction

The managerial process in preschool educational institutions should be well organized, carried out systematically. Every educator, teacher and professor in the entire education system must be both a good specialist in the field and a good pedagogue. Only by combining these two qualities, the teaching staff will fulfill their task of high responsibility and honor in the training of the young generation in good conditions. The multidisciplinary training and specialization of the teacher in didactic and managerial activity entitles him to become the designer, organizer and manager in perfect control of all the determining factors that lead to the educational modeling of the child from the earliest age. In Romania, education has known several experiments under the umbrella of the reform, which in the vast majority have only aimed at beautifying the system and not a substantive structural reform, in which both the current situation of the educational system and the positive element of the old educational system, the Romanian educational tradition, the economic perspective of the country in the context of the market economy and globalization, as well as the educational ideal desired by the whole society. Pursuing the achievement of performance criteria, the quality improvement policy must stimulate not only the fulfillment of individual specifications, but must focus on creative, innovative, individual and collective effort. Along with the pandemic and the obligation to use educational platforms in teaching, many deficiencies were discovered in terms of the skills of teachers and managers in using new technologies. The pandemic has opened a new vision for change and an opportunity to modernize the entire education system.

The current study

The present study aimed to investigate the findings related to the identification of the factors that influence the increase in the quality of the entire educational process and the adaptation of a set of

measures for the modernization of the teaching-learning-evaluation system and the increase of professional (didactic) competence. Therefore, our question of was the following: Are preschool teachers prepared to apply new technologies in the teaching process? Are we ready for the digitization of education? Do the training courses currently on the market meet the needs?

In order to answer these questions, I proposed to carry out an investigative study on a representative sample of 40 teachers, both from rural and urban, state and private, with different levels of professional training. The questionnaire called C.R.U. was applied. (Human Resource Quality) in order not to influence some answers, in two initial and final phases (beginning of the semester and end of the year/semester) to be able to observe as objectively as possible the possible changes and to which factors they are due. All questionnaires were completed anonymously, in electronic format on the GoogleDocs platform. The applied questionnaire is a linear one, each person must answer all the questions, in the order in which they appear in the questionnaire, and it contains 22 items to identify the perceptions of pre-school teachers regarding professional training. The questionnaire includes both closed questions and semi-open and open questions, in order to capitalize on all types of questions and obtain as much information as possible from the subject (Source: https://www.academia.edu/33044053/Seminarul_5_chestionarul Accessed on 20.07.2022 at 17.30). The main objective was to identify the perception of the professional quality of teaching staff and the need for improvement. The questionnaire includes two sets of variables: general variables in which are captured - general characteristics of the interviewee, of the organization (items 1-6) and variables specific to the research that capture the identification of the need for continuous training and improvement by preschool teachers (items 7 -22).

Result

Following the analysis of the answers received, the results revealed that participation in continuing education courses is considered useful and very useful by 84% of the teachers. 96% of the respondents stated that they participated in continuous training courses. The majority of teachers who participated in continuous training courses believe that the concepts learned are useful and can be applied in everyday practical work. Also, 75% of the participants in continuing education courses believed that they helped them adapt to the new generation of students, 75% noticed an improvement in the instructional-educational activity and student results, and for 79% of the teachers the courses they were useful to familiarize themselves with the new teaching and learning technologies. The results of the study indicate a generally favorable attitude towards the concept of continuous training as well as the need for a more varied offer for such courses made available by the educational unit free of charge.

Discussions

In the midst of the changes brought about by the pandemic, the key elements of the reform must take into account, first of all, the development of schools as learning communities, in which the joy of learning and the atmosphere of collaboration between students, but also between students and teaching staff. Thus, didactic methods must also be diversified, translated from individual learning to collaborative learning. The paradigm of the 4 Cs – communication, collaboration, creativity, critical thinking – can be a pedagogical framework for choosing the most inspired didactic and educational interaction strategies from this point of view. As digital technology has advanced, the possibilities for its use in the educational environment have grown exponentially. The effect of digital technology on students largely depends on how these technologies are integrated into the classroom to facilitate the teaching-learning process. The literacy level of teaching staff is, from this point of view, essential in facilitating learning through the means of digital technology"(Ceobanu, C., Cucuș, C., et.all, 2020, p.47).

In 2020, the Ministry of Education and Research launched the SMART.Edu campaign, which aims to transform education for the digital age. In the presentation document of this campaign, a series of measures that should be followed in order to align with the digital norms of European education are detailed. "Digital education throughout life is more than a goal and a finality of education, but becomes an essential premise and a means for accessing and acquiring skills in all other educational fields"(<https://www.edu.ro/sites/default/files/SMART.Edu%20-%20document%20consultare.pdf>). Digital education (Ceobanu, C., Cucuș, C., et.all, 2020), represents a paradigm that follows various innovative application courses of neurocognitive sciences, with strong transformative effects at the level of the personality of education actors (teachers and students). Digital education contributes through new methods, through access to information, through the quality of information to the better development of education at any level. Regardless of the number of advantages, the development of connectivity and

other positive elements that digital education brings to the lives of children (European citizens), there are also different types of risks and disadvantages, related to data protection and security (Ceobanu, C., Cucos, C., et.al, 2020, p.83). In order to understand the concept of digital education, it is necessary to know some specialized concepts, such as the concept of digital learning, educational software, digital literacy, digital cooperation, cyberbullying, digital participation and digital teaching. The importance of continuous training of teaching staff is given by the need to update knowledge and professional skills, increase the quality of the educational act by adapting to new technologies. However, there is a large discrepancy between the training courses that teachers often follow and the skills they need: ICT skills for teaching, new technologies in the workplace, individualized learning strategies and the formation of interdisciplinary skills in students, and so on. In order to be able to react to the changing pace and demands, teachers need adequate support and the opportunity to follow continuous training activities, in which they develop lifelong learning skills and collaborate with colleagues. The modernization and improvement of education and didactic technology is an objective necessity of all teachers in order to be able to keep up with the current generation. It is a priority to identify the deficiencies in the professional training of teachers by means of a SWOT analysis, a questionnaire or a focus group in each school unit in order to identify the most suitable improvement programs. Teacher training activities aim at objectives and contents that have a direct impact on the educational process carried out in the school and are centered on the main pedagogical approaches, respectively: analysis, design, implementation, evaluation and improvement/development of the process.

Conclusions

Preschool teachers are concerned with training, but a practical approach to content is needed with an emphasis on the integration of new technologies and the application of educational software, virtual games, ppt presentations.

We can say that the changes produced in society and the forecast of the acceleration of changes lead not only to the continuous adaptation of educational systems to the new economic, social and cultural realities, but also to the formation within these systems of the capacity for continuous regulation and self-perpetuation of adaptability. In order to face the challenges of the contemporary world, teachers must learn continuously, adequately, quickly and efficiently, innovatively, making the most of their potential. Continuous training becomes a permanent necessity regardless of the professional field and the level of training.

References

Ceobanu, C., Cucos, C., et.al

2020,

Educația Digitală, Editura Polirom, Iași

Cole, G. A.

2000,

Managementul personalului, trad. Smaranda Nistor, București : CODECS.

Gazier, B.

2003,

Strategiile resurselor umane, trad. Ruxandra Petrovici, Institutul European, Iași.

Nicolescu, O., Verboncu, I.

1993,

Fundamentele managementului organizației, București: Tribuna Economică

Nicolescu, O.

2004,

Managerii și managementul resurselor umane, București : Economică

Ministerul Educației și Cercetării

2020

STRATEGIA PRIVIND DIGITALIZAREA EDUCAȚIEI DIN ROMÂNIA, Document în consultare publică în perioada 18 decembrie 2020 – 15 februarie 2021

<https://www.edu.ro/sites/default/files/SMART.Edu%20-%20document%20consultare.pdf>